

DESIGN OF A PROGRAMMABLE HEARING AID DEVICE

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Abstract: *The hearing phenomenon is an important aspect of human experience as it helps to perceive life via the ears which is one of the sensing organs of the body. As with other realities in the world, the existence of wear and tear cannot be undermined which could have different impairment rate on individuals. Such impairment as partial or total decline in the quality of hearing could be caused by accidents, aging, misuse of ears and hereditary which could impact the social nature of individuals with such condition hence the need for a design of a hearing aid device. The design architecture involves interfacing a miniaturized microphone transducer circuit with an ATmega328P microcontroller to implement a digital based hearing aid device for hard to hear persons. The system was simulated on Proteus 8 Professional, version 8.4, mimicking the different sections of the circuit in view of the hardware implementation.*

1. Introduction

The interaction with our world is ultimately shaped by the information received via seeing, hearing, touching, smelling, or tasting and when perceived rightly an appropriate response is given in such situation. The art of hearing therefore requires a medium through which sound waves are received for interpretation in the human brain (that is the auditory nerves).

However, as a result of malfunction, deterioration or total breakdown of the ears, also known as hearing loss, the hearing effectiveness depreciates either in amplitude or frequency (Krug *et al.*, 2016; Zoghba *et al.*, 2025). Two classes of hearing losses are identified which are the conductive and sensorineural. The conductive hearing loss (CHL) is due to mechanical problems that appear in the outer or

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middle ear which affects the ear ossicle or abnormal vibration of the ear drum (Mathers *et al.*, 2000; Gustafson *et al.*, 2014). The sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) however is

associated with the malfunctioning of the inner ears as far as the nerve endings as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Anatomy of the Human Ear (<https://blog.chsc.org/blog/how-hearing-works-06/06/2025>)

The SNL defects are mostly observed and if unchecked can lead to potentially devastating chronic health condition. Similarly in a situation where there occurs a simultaneous dysfunctionality in the outer, middle or inner ears this is referred to as the mixed hearing loss (MHL) (Rana *et al.*, 2012; Coco *et al.*, 2025). A means to correct or manage this physical challenge of hearing loss is by introducing a hearing aid device at low cost. Earlier designs featured the behind-the-ear (BTE) and the in-the-ear (ITE) hearing aid device as far back into the 1960s which serves as the bedrock for various hearing aid implants.

Generally, the hearing aid device comprises of a miniaturized microphone circuit, preamplifier, microcontroller, ladder configuration circuit, output amplifier stage, speakers or earpiece and power supply. The microcontroller-based hearing aid device serves as a real time device which operates on optimized power suitable for handling varying type of hearing defects. This in contrast with the analog design which responds to the amplification of signals in the all-pass band range hence giving some form of discomfort, has optimal adaptive capabilities achieved through an effective design of an appropriate filter bank.

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The human ear is composed of the outer or external, middle and inner ear; with the external extending from the pinna (auricle) to the external auditory canal which serves to protective the middle and internal section of the ears. The middle ear is an air-filled section consisting of three (3) ossicles (malleus, incus and stapes also referred to as the hammer, anvil and stirrup respectively) they transduce

vibrations as shown in Figure 2 from the tympanic membrane (Eardrum) to the oval (elliptical) window of the fluid-filled cochlea. The inner ear however includes, the cochlea, vestibular apparatus, and the vestibule cochlear known as the acoustic nerve or cranial nerve. The base of the cochlea responds to high frequency sounds, and the apex responds to low frequency sounds (Kumar, 2014).

Figure 2. Ear and Sound Pressure

The sound waves are conducted via the external ear and auditory canal to the tympanic membrane hereby setting it on vibration while the ossicles receive the transmitted vibrations and transduce it. Sound waves can also be conducted to the inner ear through bone when the skull is acoustically stimulated. However, if the sound wave conducted through the bone is

not heard properly, then there exists disturbance in the cochlea or central auditory pathway. The mean hearing loss is therefore calculated separately for each ear as the mean values at frequencies 500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz and 4 kHz. Table 1 shows the grade of hearing impairment corresponding to the mean hearing loss and the clinical findings.

Table 1: World Health Organisation (WHO) Classification of the severity of hearing impairment

Grades of Hearing Impairment	of Mean Hearing Loss in Pure Tone Audiogram	Clinical findings	Recommendations
0- Impairment	No 25 dB or better	No or very slight hearing problems. Able to hear whispers	Counselling, follow up examination, evaluation for surgery if conductive loss is present.
1- Impairment	Slight 26-40 dB	Able to hear and repeat words spoken in normal voice at 1 meter.	Counselling, hearing aid may be advisable, surgical treatment if conductive or combined hearing loss is present.
2-Moderate Impairment	41-60 dB	Able to hear and repeat words spoken in normal voice at 1 meter.	Hearing aid is recommended, surgical treatment if conductive or combined hearing loss is present.
3- Impairment	Severe 61-80 dB	Able to hear and repeat words spoken in normal voice at 1 meter.	Hearing aid is needed else, a cochlear implant. Lip reading and signing is needed for supportive treatment.
4- Impairment including deafness	Profound 81 dB or higher	Unable to hear and understand even a shouted voice	Failure of a hearing aid trial implies an indication for a cochlear or brainstem implant, lip reading and signing can be taught in addition

Suitable system designs explore the analog and digital technologies (Akangbe *et al.*, 2024, Yusuf *et al.*, 2013, Owojori *et al.*, 2021a, Owojori *et al.*, 2021b, Owojori *et al.*, 2021c) with the analog device implemented in multistage amplifier circuit design. The only challenge is when the voice signal and noise signal are amplified equally leading to the need for a design infrastructure which enables the use of digital

signal processing (DSP) (Hall and Hasler, 2005; Curran and Galster, 2013; Chopade 2017; Lin *et al.*, 2019; Owojori *et al.*, 2019, Owojori *et al.*, 2024). This system design requires the use of a programmable device as shown in Figure 3 along some major circuit components in order words the analog signal can be modified into a digital form or sequence of discrete samples via an algorithm.

Figure 3. Programmable or Microcontroller unit

2. Experimental Setup

The system consists of four main parts namely; the acoustic or audio sensing unit, controller unit (which is the brain of the system), output amplification stage, and power supply. The circuit connection is divided into power lines and signal lines where the power lines supply DC

power to the system. A portion of the input power line is fed to the audio sensing unit, controller unit and output amplification stage. The signal lines are used to link small voltage signals from the sensing unit to the microcontroller and then to the output unit.

2.1. Sensing Unit

The sensing circuit having an electronic configuration utilizes a miniaturized microphone integrated with a pre-amplification circuit which attracts surrounding sound signals into the transducer. Since the input audio signal has a weak signal strength, an audio amplifier is included in the circuit. The audio circuit

configuration acts as an active subsystem which requires a supplied voltage (V_{cc}) of 5 V used to drive the onboard amplifier IC. A measured audio signal strength of 250 mV was observed at the microphone input via an oscilloscope and modeled using a signal generator on Proteus. The overall sensing unit is depicted in Figure 4

Figure 4. Illustrates the overall sensing unit of a hearing aid device

This subsystem is an off-the-shelf module which consist of an eletret mini-microphone represented with a signal generator, input audio filter model, micro-transistor configuration and

op-amp circuit which intended to detect and amplify the input signal either in inverting or non-inverting configuration mode. The output of the transistor stage and the corresponding signal representation from the oscilloscope are as shown in Figure 5 and 6.

Figure 5. Micro-transistor circuit configuration

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Figure 6. Micro-transistor output response

This subsection was then compacted as a sine wave signal with similar characteristics and fed to the op-amp with the introduction of DC-offset configuration as illustrated in Figure 7. The DC offset was introduced to the circuit with coupling capacitor before the controller unit with its design targeted to position the lowest value of the

signal to 0 V which is effective for signals inputted to the microcontroller. The circuit configuration depicts a voltage divider circuit with equal resistance value. With modification in the output equation the output value is scaled up to negate the negative signal in the system which is suitable for the microcontroller.

Figure 7. Introduction of DC-offset configuration

2.2. Controller and Output Signal Acquisition Unit

The microcontroller unit also known as an embedded system acts as a mini computer which processes the input signal from the DC-offset while received through the AO (Analog) pin as shown in Figure 8. The device has the ability to digitize analog signal using an inbuilt analog to

digital converter (ADC) while some of the I/O terminals possesses the pulse width modulation (PWM) signal outputs. The microcontroller deployed in this design was the Arduino Nano which operates with voltage between 5-12 V, has a reference voltage of 5 V used to set the ADC and with a chosen bit (B), the signal resolution can be obtained along with the signal equivalent

corresponding to the analog signal as expressed in Equations 1 and 2.

$$N = 2^B \quad (1)$$

$$C_{val} = \frac{(v_{in} \times V_{ref})}{(2^B - 1)} \quad (2)$$

Using the Arduino IDE interface, instruction code was generated to process the analog input signal into the Arduino and convert the analog signal into its digitized equivalent

```
float analogPinP1 = A0;
int sensorValue = 0;
float voltage;
int minValue,maxValue;
void setup()
{Serial.begin(9600);
pinMode(analogPinP1, INPUT);
}
void loop()
sensorValue = analogRead(analogPinP1);
voltage = sensorValue*(5.0/1023);
voltage = map(voltage,0,15, minValue,maxValue);
```

With the Arduino analog filter library, the microcontroller is able to eliminate all background noise above 20 kHz and below 20 Hz.

Figure 8. System Interface with Controller and Output Signal Acquisition Unit

This frequency ranges informed the use of an estimated mean average filter which mimics the complementary filter where lowpass and

highpass signals pass simultaneously. Complementary filter algorithm follows the exponential moving average (EMA) formular as shown in Equation 3 where smoothing coefficients are determined.

$$EMA_{new} = EMA_{old} \times \left(1 - \left(\frac{smoothing}{1+d}\right)\right) + Value_{new} \times \left(\frac{smoothing}{1+d}\right) \quad (3)$$

Where $\left(\frac{smoothing}{1+d}\right)$ is the smoothing coefficient, EMA_{old} representing high frequency component and $Value_{new}$ representing low frequency component.

Having passed the 'voltage' signal through the filter, the digitized value is output through the Arduino I/O terminal and fed to the ($R - 2R$) ladder circuit which gives an equivalent analog signal. The output operational amplification stage placed thereafter serves as a gain control for the system via a 10 k Ω potentiometer component powered by a 5 V regulated supply from a 9 V battery. The output was further filtered and coupled to a minispeaker.

3. Results and Discussion

The system design was first modelled in simulation mode to mimic the subsections where the individual subsystem test was carried out. The hardware implementation, however intended to receive a real-time audio signal which was not included in the scope of this paper. Using the signal generator the input signal was set to a peak-to-peak voltage of 250 mV at a frequency of 3.4 kHz within the audio range as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. The signal generator input to the audio sensing unit
 The output of the overall sensing unit stage in Figure 4 was observed to have an attenuated

signal of 46 mV peak value as shown in Figure 10 while the input signal remains the same which could be caused by improper component design and simulation approximations.

Figure 10. Overall sensing unit
 With the system simply modified to accommodate the DC offset as shown in Figure 7, an output response was observed in Figure 11, which shows a tapered peak at 290 mV but again

did not negate the negative swing of the signal response as compared to the principle of the DC offset eliminating zero crossing signals. This signal was then fed to the analog input terminal of the Arduino.

Figure 11. output response of the DC-offset configuration

Considering the digitized signal output from the microcontroller after filtering, a hexadecimal signal response can be observed due to the four output terminals which are expressed in Figure 12. These are arranged in an order of D0 to D3 (4

bits) containing binary numbers or bits representing the analog signal equivalent after filtering. With the ladder configuration the digitized signals are converted back to the analog equivalent.

Figure 12. Microcontroller output to tune the ladder circuit conFigureuration

The analog signal is then output via the amplifier conFigureuration modelled to serve as a filter and gain control. Observation from the amplification output is shown in Figure 13, while

connections from the amplifier further expresses signal filtering and an interface with a earpiece or head phone jack.

Figure 13. Output amplification stage linked to a speaker jack or ear piece

4. Conclusion

This paper has identified the use of low-cost hearing aid devices as a means of managing hearing loss. The technology leverage on the sensing, microcontroller and output signal acquisition unit with other circuit facility to ensure proper signal processing to receive a high-fidelity signal from the device. The design illustrated gives the simulation to a developed hardware programable hearing aid device identifying some design flaws and corresponding signal responses. The overall system architecture involved the interface of the device to a miniaturized microphone with a biased voltage in a circuit subsystem. Digital signal processing stage was introduced through an ATmega328P microcontroller on an Arduino which is programmed in C as instruction code to filter out irrelevant frequencies based on the complementary filter algorithm and finally outputting a digitized signal through the I/O terminal of the controller. Furthermore, the

output was converted to its analog form and output to an ear piece or audio jack via a gain control and filter circuit.

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